

USING GRAMMAR GAMES TO ENGAGE NON-ENGLISH-MAJOR STUDENTS IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE AT HOCHIMINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF FOOD INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

This research aims at investigating the innovation of using grammar games and activities to engage non-English-major (NEM) students at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUPI) to use grammatical items in studying grammar. Doing this, the researcher hopes to enhance the effectiveness of grammar games and helps motivate NEM students in studying, for instance, listening, speaking, reading and writing and a number of other skills involved in the same game such as vocabulary and pronunciation (Lee, 2000). The results of my previous research (May 2017) on the effects of language games in teaching grammar showed that most teachers and students had positive attitudes towards grammar games. Taking advantages of students' positive attitudes and desires for playing games in studying grammar, the researcher would like to do something new in teaching grammar through game activities to stimulate students in learning and applying grammar more effectively. The process of experiment had supervised to remark the results of students' progress during 10 weeks. Based on the observation of a case study and findings from analysing the questionnaire and interview, the research makes recommendations for implementing the innovation of grammar games. Once identifying the problem of un-motivation to students' usage of grammatical structures in their communicative contexts, the researcher who implemented the bottom-up innovation in a small-scale to be based on a combination of the problem solving model and social interaction model and considered as a deliberate change in teaching and learning process at HUPI. The researcher has been the innovator and change agent of innovation, the researcher's two colleagues and two 4th year students of HUPI played the role of an implementer and adopter, 20 students in one experimental class were clients.

Key words: Grammar games, to engage non-English-major (NEM) students, communicative language, positive attitudes, bottom-up innovation

1 INTRODUCTION

Teaching grammar to NEM students at HUPI is the matter of concern of English teachers to the same format of grammar sections in current textbooks from the *Life* series that make NEM students get bored and uninterested in their learning. The innovation will discuss the shared skills through grammar game activities using and how successfully introducing gaming methodology

into grammar classes can enhance and accelerate the grammar learning process as well as different aspects of English such as language skills, vocabulary and pronunciation.

Grammar plays a very important role in student's communicative language. Grammar lessons, however, were often taught by Grammar-Translation method. Very few activities were done. Students mostly listened to teacher's explanations and then did the exercises one by one. Students might find hard achieving grammar rules and get bored easily. Teachers should switch to CLT stressing on grammar, CLT does never refuse grammar teaching, communicative competence involves knowing how to use the grammar and vocabulary of the language to achieve communicative goals, and knowing how to do this in a socially appropriate way (Thornbury, 1999, p.18). Thus grammar needs to be taught communicatively in a more pleasant and interesting way by using useful grammar game activities to encourage students to use grammatical points they have learned in their communication more effectively and successfully. That is the researcher's target of this innovation.

I carried out this research with hope to find the best way of using grammar games to make grammar lessons more meaningful and enjoyable. This study aims at answering the following research questions:

1. How should games be used effectively in English grammar classes at HUFU?
2. How much do NEM students make progress in their communicative language during using grammar games in grammar lessons?

The research began with culture contexts, then the literature review of the innovation, followed by the description of the innovation implementation and a brief introduction of using grammar games and gaming methodology engaging students in studying English. The findings and analysis were discussed toward the end of the paper with the aim to achieve maximum results in the innovation.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

With the purpose of making the research comprehensive and convincing, we now spend time considering a few relevant concepts and studies of previous researchers related to the subject.

2.1 Teaching culture context

Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUFU) is located in Ho Chi Minh City - a dynamic centre of Vietnam. Founded in 1981, it was named as a Vocational School until 2002 it was called Food Industry College, during the stage of economic and social transition to global integration and changed into HUFU in 2008. HUFU identified its objectives for progressive education and training to directly meet the needs of society. Following an educational methodology that is student-centered with an underlying philosophy of "Humanity – Unity-Forwardness- Innovation", so the manager of Foreign Language Centre always asks teachers to make a change of teaching approaches to focus on student-centered class. Teachers themselves have realized this and made a deliberate change in their own classes to engage students in learning provided that they can finish their curriculum and improve their students' language

skills. Meanwhile, very few teachers have applied grammar games as communicative activities in grammar lessons to meet students' real expectations and desires to enhance students' interests in learning grammar. Why do not teachers take advantage of students' positive attitudes towards playing game activities and exploit effective grammar games and activities to motivate teaching and learning process? The researcher would like to change from traditional and structural approaches to teach in grammar classes to enhance students' interests. The innovation can be applied in an experimental case study from bottom up in a small scale at HUFU.

2.2 Class culture context

NEM students come from other areas in the country. In multi-provincial classes, NEM students who have their own locally cultural features express different thoughts and behaviours in learning. Some of them are very active and confident; most of them are nervous, anxious and embarrassed to use the language in front of class. The classroom cultures influenced by cultures outside the classroom – e.g. conflict between teacher and student schedules, curricula - impact students' learning process (Holliday, 1994, p.162). They are tired with the monotonous format of grammar language from the textbooks, materials, teaching methods that decide the nature of classroom and lead to an appropriate methodology in teaching and learning process. Cultures take an important role to educational innovation because they are cognitive behaviours, attitudes and thinking of people (Murphy 1986 quoted in Holliday 1994, p. 260). The innovation will be influenced by cultural and human factors. According to Nicholls (1983, p.4) and White (1988, p.114) innovation can be understood as an attempt to achieve appropriate methodologies improving teaching and learning process.

School and classroom cultures at HUFU are good conditions and motivation for the innovation to take place. Teachers can make a deliberate change to the techniques or supplementary materials that meet students' needs to help them learn grammatical points and other language skills more effectively and communicatively.

2.3 Types of social change and models of innovation

The researcher carried out this innovation as a bottom-up experiment to satisfy the demands for change in the classroom influenced by internal and external agents that are the need for social change to people who recognize the need for deliberate educational change (Markee, 1997, p.42-70). The change is considered *immanent change* or self-motivated change as the researcher has raised solutions to a perceived problem of the same social system and she can act as an internal change agent and promote ownership (Nicholls 1983). The research was developed basically on both the social interaction model and the problem solving model suggested by Markee (1997, p.61-67) without any support from outside change-agents. In addition, the socio-cultural contexts that are significant factors interact to force classroom innovation positively or negatively. In the innovation process, the researcher played the role of an adopter, implementer, and also change agent while the students participated in as the clients.

2.4 The roles of stakeholders

The innovation affects a number of people who take several different social roles in the practice, not integrated, contribute their efforts to the success of research. The researcher initiated the innovation and had responsibilities for monitoring the change, she was the innovator and change agent of innovation, the researcher's two colleagues and two 4th year students of HUFU played the role of an implementer and adopter, 20 students in one experimental class were clients.

2.5 Factors to consider when having games played in class

Carrier (1980) identified a number of factors that teachers should consider when having a grammar game in the language class: which appropriate games to adopt that adapt students' enjoyment and needs; when to use the game in a class time to break the stressful mood; what to prepare for the game (material, equipment, objects, flash cards); how to organize and manage class; how long the game may last, how to solve the problems when using game. These important factors contribute to the success and effectiveness of using grammar games.

2.6 Teaching grammar in the context

Nunan (2010) pointed out that grammar teaching is frequently presented out of the context in the textbooks. Students use sentences separately not in the context. Teacher should present grammar points in the context and help students explore grammatical structures in the context so that they can know the form, meaning and use in their communication meaningfully and successfully. Teaching grammar in the context is related to CLT that put stress on pair work or group work, students will learn more effectively if participate in communicative activities actively about what are learning.

3 INNOVATION METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants

The action research was carried out with 20 sophomore students of one class at HUFU, aged from 18 to 24. The percentage of females and males in these classes was 65% and 35% respectively. The classes focused on using grammatical structures in four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) and the students took four - period sessions one week. The current textbooks are Life series.

3.2 Project procedure for a case study

The research lasted for a period of 7 weeks from 15th August to 7th November 2017 with 20 students at HUFU. The researcher follows the scheme: recognizing problems, suggesting solutions to improve the situations, conducting the process of adaptation and analysing data for the results and reflections and then giving conclusion.

3.3 Problem recognition

The researcher recognized the problem of students who are not interested in and get bored with tough grammar lessons by sitting at one place, listening to teacher's instructions, taking notes,

doing exercises in textbook one by one, memorizing lessons that de-motivate their learning. On the contrary, they have positive attitudes towards grammar game activities and they are interested in joining in different activities, enjoying the pleasant atmosphere, interacting with other students by using grammatical structures they have learned so that they can remember the lesson better. Both teachers and students recognized the important roles of grammar in their communicative language. Teachers, however, seldom used grammar game activities when teaching grammar to meet students' expectations although teachers agreed that they should use grammar game activities to motivate and engage students' interests in learning. Students confirmed that they could get a great deal of benefits from **playing games, they felt more comfortable, relaxed and enthusiastic about the lesson, games helped them remember the lesson better, more confident and active to express their ideas when they joined in the game activities** and have opportunities to practice and obtain grammar structures in communicative games.

3.4 Suggesting solutions to improve the situations

To improve teaching and learning process, the researcher wanted to apply grammar game activities to innovate the way of teaching grammar switching from traditional and structural approaches into CLT ones. The innovation with efforts lasted 7 weeks to achieve satisfying results from the case studies of the action research, the researcher had to observe her students' attitudes, feelings, reactions and reflections during the lessons when using grammar games by having class observation diaries. The questionnaire and interview were then carried out to explore the students' feelings and reactions in the language classroom; their opinions and feedbacks help clarify the answers of the research.

3.5 Plan of innovation

This innovation research was carried out during 7 weeks. The schedule was below:

Selecting grammar game activities for students to work in cooperative and collaborative learning such as in pairs, in groups and whole class appropriately and effectively.

Piloting questionnaire and revising structured interview questions.

Preparing the observation scheme: Discussing with colleagues about how to use observation scheme to supervise students' interaction during the lessons.

Pre-test (20 minutes) (see appendix 1)

The initial student questionnaire (see appendix 2)

Observation stage 1: Sessions 1, 2, 3, 4 (Work in pairs, in groups, asking and answering as instructed). Grammar games applied (see appendix 5)

Observation stage 2: Sessions 5, 6, 7, (Work in pairs, in groups, problem-solving task, whole class activities as instructed)

The follow-up student structured interview (see appendix 3)

Post-test (30 minutes) (see appendix 4)

Analysing the data, findings, reflections and conclusion.

3.6 Conducting the process

Having identified the problems and prepared a scheme for implementing the innovation, the researcher carried out the plan as follows:

Step 1:

Pre-test: Having students take a pre-test (see appendix 1) within 20 minutes before the researcher applied game activities in teaching grammar.

Step 2:

The initial student questionnaire: The questionnaire (see appendix 2) was delivered to students before implementing the research to get students' ideas, feelings and reactions with the aims of finding out more ways to motivate students to participate in game activities and engage them in communicative language.

Step 3:

Live observation with observation scheme. Applying game activities (handouts delivery - see appendix 5) in teaching grammar after teachers present the grammar points and explain the rules of grammar. The two colleagues, the researcher and two 4th year students helped observe the class during the game activities. Each person was in charge of one group of 4 students (work in groups) or two groups of 2 (work in pairs). They had to follow the interaction of students in pairs or in groups to remark and take notes the pairs or groups practice (turns talking and times talking).

The class observation diaries to apply grammar games in the class: The students at HUFU seem to be hard-working and to like studying grammar because they acknowledged the importance of grammar. Before doing innovation, the researcher found that students worked very hard during the grammar lessons, they looked stressed, got bored and felt sleepy when they studied grammar by doing exercise one by one without communication, even making separated sentences not in a context or in real communication. Furthermore, the students often felt exhausted by the end of each lesson and un-relaxed before going home or going on the next lessons. However, from the preliminary observations the researcher applied grammar games in the first session, the class atmosphere changed, the active one dominated the class where students were eager to take part in game activities and to use the grammatical structures they have learned in playing games. Most students joined in the activities enthusiastically; they had chances to use the target language for authentic communication with their friends. Then the researcher kept on using game activities in teaching grammar to engage students in teaching for next sessions. The researcher followed the observations, took notes for findings; analysis and assessment of students' progress as well as of innovation.

Step 4:

Follow-up student structured interview questions: Individual interview questions (see appendix 3) were carried out with 12 deliberately selected students who showed their feelings and

reactions during participation. The interview was done by the researcher and tape recorded (video clip) to assure the objectivity of the research.

Step 5:

After having applied game activities in teaching grammar to stimulate students in teaching grammar during 7 weeks, the researcher gave students the post-test (see appendix 4) within 30 minutes so that the researcher can assess their progress after they studied grammar through game activities in their communicative language skills.

4 DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The researcher followed and observed during the improvement for collecting data, she realized some positive and negative changes in the process.

The results of pre-test (see table 5): The result of the class was not satisfying. One student got 8 marks, two students got 7 marks, twelve students got 5-6 marks, five students got 3-4 marks. Most of students use wrong English tenses in the context and do not remember the grammatical rules.

The results of the initial student questionnaire (see appendix 2A). Twenty students agreed that they like to study grammar by joining in different activities, interacting with other students that help them become more active and confident. Twenty students did not like sitting at one place, listening to teacher's instruction, taking note, doing exercises in textbook one by one, memorizing lessons because they got bored, tired, stressed and felt sleepy. They could not engage in their communicative language. Their responses showed that they are eager to join in game activities.

From the observation: The researcher collected data from “live observation” of 10 groups of 2 and five groups of 4 they watched students carefully during their interactions and the data were analysed and found the following results.

In the 2nd observation – stage 1: Students had the handouts and worked in pairs within 10 minutes to finish the game activity. Ten groups of 2 took part in the activity enthusiastically and comfortably. They take turns to ask and answer the questions actively and express their ideas. Pairs 9 and 10 did rather well, they talked 29 and 28 times within 10 minutes while pair 6 talked only 17 times and did not finish the task with the same amount of time as their friends. (See table 1).

In the 3th observation – stage 2: Students work in groups with the handouts within 15 minutes to finish the game activity or solve the task. Five groups showed their interests in the activity, they were not anxious in speaking. Groups 1 and 3 had 32 talking turns. They helped one another to encourage shier students to take part in the activity. (See table 2).

In the 4th observation – stage 3: Students had the handouts and worked in pairs within 10 minutes to solve the task. The teacher changed the partners so that students can work with new partners. Ten groups of 2 participated in the activity and tried to use target language in the context of the game. They made a great progress in real communication, they increased their talking turns. They

talked more than they did in last observation. The pair 8 had 37 talking times within 10 minutes and pair 2 had 35 times in communicative practice. However, the pair 6 did not abuse the time for their speaking, they only did 23 turns and they wasted their time. (See table 3)

In the 5th observation – stage 4: Students had the handouts and worked in groups in 15 minutes to complete the game activity and achieve their target language to solve the task. Five groups of 4 were eager to join in the activity; they did their best to apply what they have studied in real communication. The 1st group did very well and had 38 talking times, however, there are 2 groups did not finish the task and the talking time was under 10 minutes. (See table 4)

Whole class activity observation: Students joined in the whole class activity actively. Once asked to stand up and made two circles (the big one outside and small one inside), or made two lines for practice, they were keen on applying grammatical points to express their ideas in their communication with friends to solve the task that teacher gave. Besides they could use their language in real context or real life meaningfully.

Results from the interview (Appendix 3 A) (Tape recorded – watch video clip): Twelve students agreed to apply game activities in grammar class because they enjoy very much. Ten of them want to play games every grammar lesson about 10 or 15 minutes. Twelve of them were motivated in learning; felt relaxed and confident to practice language in their communication. Moreover, they realized that game activities are not only useful for practicing grammatical points but for improving vocabulary and other skills. Those are the reasons why they want to have grammar games in the class. To evaluate the results of innovation, the researcher want to check the students' progress by the post-test after a period of experimental time.

Results of post-test: The result of the post-test was quite better. Two students got 9 marks, three students got 8, six students got 7 marks, four students got 6 marks, four students got 5 marks, one student got 4 marks, no student got 3 anymore. Most of students have known how to use structures and they improved their scores. It is proved that they make a good progress in their learning. (See table 5)

In short, the researcher assumes that teachers might determine the effect of games on their students' learning English because she recognizes and exploits culture of learning and students' attitudes in language classroom (Tutor, 2001) that helps her apply new techniques in teaching suit with students' demands. Regardless of what games and how grammar games used were helpful more or less in learning and teaching. Using grammar games is the best way of reviewing the language point students have learned, of helping students remember grammar better, of creating opportunities to practice English in active learning environment. In fact, students made good progress and improved their communicative language in speaking, listening, reading and writing. Grammar game using, however, brings about both positive and negative features. Then there are some problems should be considered when using them.

Unexpected problems and limitations when using game activities and teacher's solutions.

Using grammar games can create problems for both students and teachers.

First, students do not have enough vocabulary to express their ideas in communication. Thus, teacher should provide vocabulary related to the game activities so that students can use language in the interactions.

Second, game activities cannot be successful if the instructions of games are not clear enough and make students get embarrassed because they did not know how the games went and what procedures they had to follow. The teacher should give short and clear instructions and model the games so that students can understand what to do and how to play well.

Third, there is not enough room to rearrange desks for students to sit or to move around in the class for practice and teacher cannot move around to control students. This depends on the conditions and situations that teacher should be flexible to organize the class properly and have good class management. The teacher should ask students to work in pairs with partners next to them to avoid noise and disruption. In groups, students have to move their desks to form groups.

Fourth, using games in the classroom sometimes fails due to the lack of cooperation among members of the class. Grammar games require all students' involvement and they promote friendly competition, therefore, it needs students' cooperative attitude. Another issue is that students usually speak in their mother tongue to discuss instead of the language they are learning.

Fifth, they made a great deal of mistakes in pronunciation; they have not obtained the accuracy and fluency as expected. That helps teachers recognize the students' weak points so that teachers have the best way to help them improve in practice since "practice makes perfect".

Last problem is noise making. Some game activities will bring about excitement, noises and using mother tongue, teacher should have a good class management and arrange students in the right positions in pair-work or group-work (Walcyn-Jones, 1995, p.1) to control the activity and limit noises and make sure that students use the target language not the mother tongue to complete the communicative task. The teacher does not forget to give the specific time and set a rule for the players, players break the rules or use mother tongue (Vietnamese) are punished. Otherwise, players do well or are winners will get awards, competition can help motivate students. Besides the teachers should move around, remind them to try to use more English, correct their mistakes and help them when necessary. (watch video clip for students' participation.)

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This innovation carried out in the small scale by observations in one class at HUFU as an experimental unit and results of observation showed students have made good progress in their learning and engaged in communicative language so far. Some students, however, have not made much good progress; they need to improve their communicative language skills more and are more motivated in learning. That is the aim of the researcher.

Though there are limitations and difficulties in this innovation, the researcher did her best to overcome and adapt students' expectation to improve teaching and learning process. I learn a lot from the innovation - the good points and bad points. That is true "one must learn by doing the

thing, for though you think you know it – you have no certainty, until you try” (Sophocles, 400 B.C.E, cited in Roger 1983:163).

In order for game activities to be carried out successfully, teachers should consider some factors when using games that were not deeply researched in the study such as good preparation of games and clear instructions, length of games, classroom management, correction that contribute to the success of using grammar games (Carrier, 1980). The competition, challenge, scoring, award and punishment can be made so that students try harder (Nixon and Tomlinson, 2003, p.10). In addition, the teacher's role in most games is as monitor, moves around and gives help when needed. Teacher should not interrupt or correct immediately and spoils the atmosphere. **Teachers can refer some books about** “Grammar Games and Activities for Teachers” of Peter Watcyn-Jones (1995) and “Communicative games” of Jill Hadfield (1984, 1987, 1996) from elementary to advanced levels that help teachers have the best choice of game activities for students in each class. . By the way, teachers can visit the useful websites to download various kinds of useful grammar game activities.

The researcher had applied this innovation to the second class at HUFU and she realized that game activities could be used for other classes in teaching grammar to engage students in communicative language. Hopefully, other teachers can suggest more new techniques in teaching grammar to help students improve their learning and communicative language.

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